

An Appraisal of the Prominence of Comparative Religion and Religious Dialogue as Powerful Key to Conflicts Resolutions in Northern Nigeria

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Abstract

Religion is an indispensable aspect of every human person. It pervades every activity of man both in sports, agriculture, entertainment, education, politics, business activity and many others. Religion has aided social progress, educational development, interpersonal and international co-operation as well as mutual understanding among people. However, in contemporary time, religion has been rather employed to perpetrate crime, insecurity and destroy lives and properties by religious extremists, fundamentalists, bigotry, fanaticism and many other factors. Using phenomenological approach, the study undertakes to examine the gospel of comparative religion and religious dialogue for conflict resolution in Northern Nigeria to assess its values in the mixed of traditional and cultural change in the contemporary Nigerian society. The study adopted historical, description and e methods and data were gathered from both primary and secondary sources. Findings from the study revealed that, most of the violence attacks and bloodshed that are being experienced in Northern Nigeria today have religious undertones. Findings also revealed that rather than employing as a means to attain a healthy and blissful end, religion is now employed as a means to destroy lives and properly in contradiction to its perceived essence. This study opted that, the knowledge of religious dialogue, peace education and doctrinal teachings from the study of comparative religion are potent tools for resolving religious conflicts and violent attacks in a pluralistic society like Nigeria. The research concluded that tolerance is a veritable panacea to attain the desired peaceful co-existence, stability and development in Northern Nigeria. The study further recommended that, religious re-orientation through the teaching of comparative religion and religious dialogue be employed in all formal and informal educations by engaging in inter-faith dialogue at community levels, government agencies and non-governmental organisations in order to achieved the desired peace, harmony and development in Northern Nigeria and beyond.

Keywords: Religion, Religious Conflicts, Comparative Religion, Religious Dialogue, Peace and Development

Introduction

Religion as a matter of fact and as held by the generality of humankind is supposed to be a machinery for peace, stability, harmony and development. This is made evident in the various doctrines preached by the various religious faiths. Christianity for instance preaches love and this has cut across all spheres of life. While Islam preaches peace¹ It is however noted with greater dismay that, religion has not been able to achieve its supposed goals in enhancing the said love, peace, stability, harmony and development that its professed. It is argued here that, the inability of the leaders of these religious sects to accommodate one another is the cause of the various and persistent religious conflicts or crises experienced in Nigeria today.²

The fact however is that, these religions professed in one God though with different religious orientation, faith and doctrines but they are still linked up in some areas. It is against this background that the study posed the following question for investigations. What are the factors that hindered peaceful co-existence among the adherents of these major religions in Northern Nigeria? What are those common attributes do they share? What machinery can be used to resolve the problem of religious intolerance among the adherents of the two religions? The above questions constitute the problem which the study set out to explore and to find lasting solutions to it. Hence the study undertakes to clearly demonstrate how the study of comparative religion through religious re-orientation and dialogue can foster peace, harmony and stability among different religious traditions in Nigeria.

Understanding Key Terms and Concepts

Religion: Religion according to Anyacho is derived from two Latin words *religio* meaning sacredness, piety, or fear of the

supernatural and *religale* which means to hold together, to bind or fasten.³ Ekarika considered religion as an act that one has carefully observed, chosen and bound to, in worship and loving care.⁴ Religion therefore denotes man's experience, awareness, attitude, recognition, conception, and understanding of the existence of the supernatural or the multiplicity of spiritual beings and his relationship or interaction with them.⁵ Religion can better be understood as a regulated pattern of life of a people in which experiences, beliefs and knowledge are reflected in man's conception of himself in relation to others, his social world, the physical as well as the metaphysical world. The elements of beliefs and practices with the former finding expression in the latter are common even with concepts outside religion.⁶ However, from which angle or no matter how one defines religion, two elements stand out clearly: beliefs and practices of a people. Affirming the above Radcliff Brown opines "any religion normally involves certain ideas or beliefs on the one hand, and on the other, certain observances."⁷

Religious Conflicts: According to Kadayifci, religious conflicts are conflicts that often take place among religious communities that live in close proximity and whose histories are filled with hostility, resentment, trauma and violence.⁸ Conflict is a struggle over values and claims to scarce resource status, power and resources in which the aims of the opponents are to neutralise, injure or eliminate the rivals. It entails a physical confrontation between parties.⁹ By religious conflict, it means a situation in which the relationship between members of one religious group and another are characterised by lack of cordiality, peaceful co-existence, mutual suspicion and fear, and a tendency towards violent confrontation.

Conflicts Resolution: Conflicts resolution does not imply conflicts management. Conflicts resolution minimises the negative outcomes of conflicts and promotes the positive outcomes of conflicts with the goal of improving learning in an organisation. Properly managed conflicts increase organisational learning by increasing the number of questions asked and encourage people to challenge the status quo. Conflicts resolution is the practice of being able to identify and manage conflicts sensibly, fairly, and efficiently.

Development: The term 'development' is normally understood to be a process for changing economic and social capacities, priorities and choices. In common parlance, it means well-being and better life for people at large. For many 'development' is also a desire for fulfillment of basic needs both for the sustenance (food, cloth, house, employment, health, education, safety, security etc.) as well as for the comfort (better services, communication, freedom, openness, mobility, dignity, etc.). There is little uniformity amongst most of us about what constitute the basic and immediate needs. Pieterse has attempted to define development as 'the organised intervention in collective affairs according to a standard of improvement'. Thus, that did not prevent him from recognising that 'what constitutes improvement and what is appropriate intervention vary according to class, culture, historical context and relations of power.'¹¹

Comparative Religion: Comparative Religion is a field of study that analyses the similarities and differences of themes, rituals, teachings and doctrines among world religions. Graeve gave a comprehensive definition of the comparative study of religions as the branch of the non-normative study of religions that investigates scientifically the similarities and differences between various religions or religious phenomena.¹⁰ Comparative religion can also be seen as the study of religions concerned with the systematic comparison of the doctrines and practices of the world's religions. Engaging in such exercise gives one a richer and more sophisticated understanding of human beliefs and practices regarding the sacred, numinous, spiritual and divine.

Similarly, is a field of study that always seeks to derive general principles from a comparison and classification of the growth and influence of various religions.¹¹ It is also considered to be the study of different religions in order to know how they relate to each other. It examines similarities, differences and the way in which different religions interact and complement each other. It studies how various religious groups have found themselves coming into closer contact with one another on both personal and social levels. Comparative religion can also be seen as the study of religions concerned with the systematic comparison of the doctrines and practices of the world's religions. Engaging in such exercise gives one a richer and more sophisticated understanding of human beliefs and practices regarding the sacred, numinous, spiritual and divine.¹²

Religious Dialogue: The concept dialogue simply means to establish a contact and communication between two or more persons or communities or nations. Dialogue according to Massoudi is an encounter between two or more human beings.¹³ While balancing individual emotions with other, Czubaroff went further by defining how the encounter transpires "to acknowledge and respond to the address of the other in the light of her own experience truth."¹⁴ Religious dialogue refers to the dialogue that occurs between official representatives of particular religious traditions in an intentional, natural and local encounter.¹⁵ Inter-religious dialogue involves active engagement across differences to seek understanding through

reciprocal communication. Swindler state that, Inter-religious dialogue is a conversation between individuals or persons and through them, two or more communities or groups with differing views, the primary purpose of this encounter is for each participant to learn from the other so that they can change and grow for communities as well.¹⁶ Inter-religious dialogue is a meeting of people of differing religions, in an atmosphere of freedom and openness, in order to listen to the other, to try to understand that person's religion, and hopefully to seek possibilities of collaboration.

Inter-Faith Dialogue according to Anyacho is a tool that fosters a better understanding between different faith groups and promotes peaceful co-existence¹⁷. According to Arinze, inter-faith dialogue is a meeting of people of different religions in an atmosphere of freedom and openness, in order to listen to the others, to try to understand that person's religion, and to seek for collaborations.¹⁸ Taken at face value, "inter-faith dialogue is the encounter and interaction among individuals and/or families who practice differing faith traditions."¹⁹ These views pointed out that inter-faith and inter-religious dialogue between Christians and Muslims is the same tool that has the potentials to promote mutual understanding of other's belief, or to engage in a common study of each other's scriptures. Thus, Christian-Muslim Dialogue refers to the building up of a relationship between Christians and Muslims with an attempt to overcome doctrinal and mutual prejudices in order to enhance tolerance, unity and peaceful co-existence among them.²⁰ It also refers to the dialogue that occurs between official representatives of particular religious traditions in an intentional encounter

Peace: Peace simply means the absence of fear, conflict, anxiety, suffering and violence. It is primarily concerned with creating and maintaining a just order in society and the resolution of conflict by non-violent means.²¹ Oke on the other hand defines peace as a process involving activities that are directly or indirectly linked to increasing development and reducing conflict, both within specific societies and in the wider international community.²² To add to the above, peace can also be seen as an ideal state which is characterised by a total absence of conflicts or as the absence of war.

Peace can be seen as an ideal state characterised by a total absence of conflict, as a frozen state of rest, or as the absence of war. However, from whatever we define peace; it is a process involving activities that are directly or indirectly linked to increasing development and reducing conflict, both within specific societies and in the wider international community.²³ Meanwhile, to add to the above, peace can also mean the absence of fear, conflict, anxiety, suffering and violence. It is primarily concerned with creating and maintaining a just order in society and the resolution of conflict by non-violent means.

Harmony and Stability: Harmony as defined by *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* means "a state of agreement in feelings, interest, opinions et cetera. It also means a pleasing combination of related things."²⁴ For example, working towards harmony in international affairs, live together in harmony. While stability according to *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary*, is the quality or state of being stable. Thus, stable means to be firmly established; not likely to fail or change; steady, not easily upset or disturbed; balanced.²⁵

The Place of Religion in Northern Nigeria

Religion is a special phenomenon in human life; it is an option that cannot be ignored. There is no other concept or phenomenon in human history which molds and controls man's life as much as religion does. It is most obvious that both men and women in attempt to practice religion have given up not only their possession but also their lives; in an attempt to inherit the hereafter, they have renounced their possessions and turned themselves into beggars, and some even die in the process. Thus, religion has a powerful grip on man that is cannot be ignored in human society. In line with the above fact, the concept of God is cardinal to the issue of religion. The nature of God is an incomprehensible mystery such that different religions perceive Him differently.²⁶ It is not possible for any religion to hold entire or absolute knowledge of God because each of them has their own fragmental and limited knowledge about God. In other words, it is impossible for any man or any religion to so grasp God in His entirety, since knowing Him is a mystery.

Religious crisis is a disagreement or disunity between two groups or one religion and or different religious groups that militate against coherent existence or practice within or without themselves. This situation has existed from time immemorial. For example, conflicts can arise within Christianity or Judaism or Islamism et cetera. And in such cases, it has resulted to factions and denomination. In this research, focus is majorly on Christianity and Islam. The historical encounters between the adherents of Christianity and Islamic religions in Northern Nigeria have often been violent, as one group seeks to impose its will on another and claimed superiority over another.²⁷ Even in societies where two or more groups seem to co-exist, the majority population will tend to exert its power over the minorities and members of minority groups live in a perpetual state of discrimination.

In such struggles, the "other" is usually depicted by each of the groups through stereotypes, where certain

characteristics (almost always negative) are exaggerated and generalised as if all members of that group were stamped from the same mold.²⁸ These inter-group relationships are characterised by a hierarchy of power and inter-group communication takes place in a competitive context, where the strongest is most likely to prevail there by imposing its ideologies on the other.

Albert Isaac argued that, Nigeria is one of the most heterogeneous societies, because her religious character is a pointer to that effect. Before the coming of Islam and Christianity during the pre-colonial Nigeria, the inhabitants were religiously very heterogeneous.²⁹

In the different societies that have merged to form the entity called Nigeria today, religion played integrative roles. The different people had similar concepts of the Supreme Being and believed in the intermediary deities and spirits who provided social, political and moral guidance. Membership of this society was such as being synonymous with religious identification.³⁰ Since the people of the various tribal groups had similar belief systems, religion was able to serve as a rank of identifying or distinguishing members of different groups (the role of religion).

From time immemorial, man had been communing with his creator through prayers. But the mode by which this is done varies. However, one thing had stood out very clearly and that is freedom which enables anybody to choose his or her own mode of worship. These days, this freedom seems threatened by some religious zealots. They want to force others to accept their own mode of worship (mostly Islamic religion) as the only acceptable one. Consequently, it is widely accepted that, of all religions in Nigeria, Islam maintained the record of being the most bloody and controversial by the demonstration of faiths. This assertion may be regarded as a historical legacy rather than an aberration. Right from time immemorial, Islamic activities have been associated with violence as a means of purification as unification of its followers. Unfortunately, thus religious violence grows in intensity owing to the surprising doctrine that one who stubbornly dies in the course of fighting the infidels will inevitably find himself in “Aljiesia” (Heaven or paradise).³¹

Religion has been described as the opium of the poor several decades ago. The truism of this statement has much to do with the fact that religion has been a powerful element in the life of man since the beginning of time propelling him and directing his affairs absolutely. Philosophers and mystics have labored to conceptualise the true essence of religion. In approaching religion, there exists diversity in the characteristics and attitudes of adherents of particular religions, sympathisers and critics. Nigeria has always been a pluralistic state with very diverse ethnic, religious, cultural linguistics, economic and social characteristics. In spite of these diversities, Nigerians have tried to live more or less in harmony tolerating each other’s religious beliefs. The phenomena of religious crises are recent developments, which obviously have been fueled by self-seeking individuals and groups to feather their selfish interest.

Thus, we are confronted with realities whereby some of the so-called religious crises are indeed not religious in origin but have ethic and political undertones. Religion is exploited in this manner because it is the most vulnerable since adherents of the various religions, which are considered divine, can be very easily manipulated to fight for “God’s cause” dogmatically without reservation. Most world religions believe in the concept of a supreme God that directs and oversees the affairs of the world. He also metes out punishments to those who go against his commandments except if they renounce their wrong doing and seek forgiveness from this most High Being. In Islam, He only needs to say “be” and it will be. In the Bible, God said “let there be light and there was light” (Genesis 1: 3). This belief should as a matter of act engender a spirit of love, cooperation and understanding between adherents of the great religions of the world.

This is neither the only point of congruence between the two most popular religions in the world nor indeed between the multitudes of all religions of the world. All world religions preach peace. There is no religion that propagates violence as part of its doctrine. Religion in its true sense is a way of life that has nothing to do with hatred and any form of oppression that breeds violence and as a matter of fact, should, engender instead good neighbourliness, universal love and moral religious believe that on judgment day this happily, should and must serve as a sort of needed restraint on the actions of humans the world over. Essentially, therefore, religion should be practiced faithfully and should bring out the goodness in man to the fore.

If we accept this assertion as we of course ought to, being true adherents of the divine teachings of our sacred faiths, it must then become crystal clear to most discerning minds that those who use religion to foment crisis and chaos in Nigeria, merely manipulate ignorant followers of their faith into violence to protect and propagate their selfish political and social interest. This realisation, more than any should make us see religion as a powerful unifying force and a catalyst for the development of man and his society.³² In this sense, religion is therefore a versatile tool for the brotherhood and indeed sisterhood among all mankind. The diversity in our religions therefore should be a source of strength and unity amongst uses aptly captured in our society

Religious crisis in Northern Nigeria has a lot of telling affect. The United States Commission on International Religious Freedom (CIRF) has decided to blacklist Nigeria as one of the world's worst abusers of religious freedom. The Commission asserted that the tolerance by Nigeria's federal, state and local governments of systematic, ongoing and egregious violations of religious freedom has created a climate of impurity, resulting in thousands of deaths.³³ Religious tolerance and our peaceful co-existence will continue to be a problem due to the way and manner we have carried on with our faith and beliefs. A recent advertisement looking for those who would want to make a career in the Christian ministry stated the required quality: aggressive, they would need this quality so as to penetrate villages, cities, offices and wherever people can be found. The Muslims also exhibit this quality.

Being aggressive had led to the noise around us today when these adherents are worshipping. At some Churches and Mosques, the loudspeakers are placed outside and the one ministering will be shouting as if in a competition to shout louder than the others. This is combined with beating of bands and singing and shouting by all those present. This form of worship goes on both day and night causing those in the neighbourhood to lose their sleep after a hard day's struggle. Others flagrantly close high ways and even express ways all in the name of worship. These attitudes breed contempt for a religion and hatred for the adherent. They are also among the fuel that keeps religious intolerance burning in the contemporary times.³⁴

Tools for Resolving Religious Crises in Northern Nigeria

Comparative study of religion with its basic principles is discovered to be the most effective tools for resolving religious crisis/conflicts among various religions in order to maintain peace, harmony and stability in the country. History records that, the comparative study of religions originated in the nineteenth century when scholarly and historical analysis of the Bible had flourished, and when Hindu and Buddhist texts were first being translated into European languages. Early influential scholars included Friedrich Max Muller, in England and Cornelius, P. Tiele, in the Netherlands champion to course of this study. Today, comparative religion study is practiced by scholars worldwide. In its early years, it was known as comparative religion or the science of religion and, in the United States of America, there are those who today are also know in the field as "the history of religion" (associated with methodological traditions traced to the University of Chicago in general, and in particular, Mircea Eliade, from the late 1950s through to the late 1980s).³⁵

Comparative religion is concerned with the systematic comparison of the doctrines and practices of world's religion. It yields a deeper understanding of the fundamental theosophical concerns of religion such as ethics, metaphysics and the nature and form of salvation. Studying is meant to give one a richer and more sophisticated understanding of human beliefs and practices regarding the sacred, numinous, spiritual and divine.³⁶ Also, Mark observes that comparative religion can be understood from religious pluralism which means "respecting the otherness of others."³⁷

It is an attitude or policy regarding the diversity of religious belief systems co-existing in society. The world view according to which one's religion is not the sole and exclusive source of truth, and thus the acknowledgement that at least some truths and true values exist in other religions. It also means the acceptance of the concept that two or more religions with mutually exclusive truth claims are equally valid. This is a form of toleration, a condition of harmonious co-existence between adherents of different religions.³⁸ Comparative religion provide adequate and concrete information on the tenets and nature of different faith s and philosophy which now have votaries in Nigeria particularly and the global village at large. Also to transfer such data to others, so they can complement instead of conflicting each other. In other words, the knowledge of comparative religion would to a large extent help in reducing religious crises.

Describing the Northern Nigerian experience, Malachy Ike observed that Nigeria is a large country with a population of over one hundred million people³⁹. That been the case, it is one of the many countries "endowed" or perhaps better put "burdened" with multifarious religious beliefs and practices. Although, there are numerous religions in Nigeria, traditional religion, Christianity and Islam easily stand out as the three major religions in Nigeria, there would have been no problem about multiplicity of religious faiths in Nigeria were it possible for each to exist without contact with each other.⁴⁰ These religions exist in the same society called Northern Nigeria and as such they are bound to interact with one another. Just as relations between one individual and another are inevitable so are relations between and among different groups be they social, cultural, political, or religious.

As earlier noted, the significance of religion in the maintenance of peace, harmony, stability and development in Northern Nigeria cannot be overemphasised. The notion of religion itself suggests an assumption that human perceptions of things, whims and caprices require higher powers to help them respond adequately and effectively to all their concern. God is the subject of the religious experience, and God is the summary of all good, he is the epitome of goodness and every

moral uprightness. Every comparative religion teaches that the only way to the harbour of delights, which is the ultimate destination of all, is uprightness, love, justice, and mercy, which are all attributes of God. This participation in the divine attribute is the ticket to heaven. Not only that, it is the path to social equilibrium and thus ethnic harmony in Nigeria since all members of the various ethnic groups in Nigeria are adherents of one religion or the other.

It therefore means that belief in the Supreme Being extends to other aspects of human existence. It equally provides a guide to 'dos' and 'don'ts' to man in order to live a meaningful life and reverence the Creator. Most of these guidelines are stipulated in the Holy Bible, the Quran and traditional religion or values and norms. The two holy books and traditional doctrinal pattern openly stipulates how man must live on earth with regard to protection of lives and property. To this extent, it could be argued that there is largely an interaction between religion and the Nigerian society within which it functions. Religion influences policies and general societal ordering and affects the behavior of the individual and confers on the individual a form of identity in the society to the extent that it colours human relations.

Consequently, because of its tendency to colour human relations, religion, if positively applied, can play significant roles in the entire social process especially in multi-religious and multi-ethnic society as Nigeria. The functional perspective of religion which reflects in the writings of scholars as Emile Durkheim among others, see religion as performing the functional role of reinforcing the collective conscience of the society requisite for social order and national stability. Religion, after all, is a powerful instrument for mobilising public opinion and a constituent of cultural norms and values, and because it addresses the most profound existential issues of human life, religion is deeply implicated in individual and social conceptions of peace, harmony and stability.⁴¹ This is why the preambles to Nigeria, America and other constitutions open with reference to God and the American motto reads "in God we trust". This means man's existence on earth is premised on religion, on the Supreme Being, God.

With special reference to traditional religion, most of the social checks and balances in traditional social structures have the tinge of religion. Many of the conceptual schemes that sustains the socio-economic and political cohesion and life of these societies have a deep religious taproot, which checkmates any tendency to patronise unwarranted and socially unapproved behaviours. Without these religious safeguards in a multi-ethnic society like Nigeria, the concourse of social interaction would be fraught (as it presently is in Northern Nigeria) with danger, violence, ethnic chauvinism, which could lead to disintegration. Hence, religion is deployed to ensure the survival of the common weal.

Christianity advocates one being his brother's keeper and love of one's neighbor, even his enemies. The Holy Bible in Exodus 20: 13-17 itemised the laws. Verse 13 specifically states "you shall not murder", verse 15 says "you shall not steal". Islam on the other hand has as the foundation of its belief system; peace and its Quranic peace passage are overwhelming. Allah Almighty says a lot on living together with other people who practice other religions than Islam. The Prophet Mohammed put into practice the Quranic injunctions in dealing with non-Muslims. Quran 60:8 says "Allah does not forbid you with regards to those who do no fight you in your religion, nor drive you out of your homes forcefully, to deal kindly and justly with them: Allah loves those who are just". Allah has emphasised oneness of humankind. In Quran 49:13, Allah says: "O mankind, we created you from a single (pair) of male and female, and make you into nations and tribes that you may understand each other."⁴²

Suffice it to say that, the scriptural passages so far examined together remind us of our common membership in the human family and of our cultural diversity. Differences of religion are normal phenomenon of life because we are not all the same now and we can never be. These passages challenge Muslims and Christians with the obvious facts of religious pluralism as evidence that demands acceptance and compliance. The concept of justice derived from God in various religions is a right of individual citizens. It is therefore one of the fundamental bases for peace and peaceful co-existence among people of various religions. Religion is a vital stabiliser of human life and it is centered deeply in the human genetic and ontological blueprint. It is therefore suggested here that a little practical religiosity would change Nigeria for the needed peace, stability and harmony in Nigeria.

The Basic Principles of Comparative Religion

The following are the basic principles of comparative religion that are used in the maintain peace, harmony and stability in the country. These include:

1. Religious Dialogue: this is one of the basic principles of comparative religion. For there to be sustained peace, stability and harmony in Northern Nigeria, there must be dialogue between these religions: Christianity and Islam. The religious leaders must come together and chart a new course of action to be followed nay pursued by its adherents. Though there have been some efforts towards dialogue, but, these efforts must be proactive. Such efforts as that on the 20th of October, 2011,

where President Goodluck Jonathan called an extra ordinary meeting of Nigeria Inter-Religious Council (NIREC) at Abuja to appeal to religious leaders to see ways of using religion to restore peace and promote peaceful co-existence in Nigeria. The meeting revealed that the Nigerian Government is passionate about dialogue to ensure peace and harmony.⁴³

Furthermore, even international communities are becoming interested in assisting Nigeria to fight religious crises through dialogue in November 18-19, 2011. The UFUK Dialogue Foundation organised the international conference at the Transcorp Hilton, Abuja with the theme: *Establishing a Culture of Co-existence and Mutual understanding*. Also, on March 3, 2012, the Canadian Embassy called a meeting of a few scholars to a discussion on what the Canadian Government can do to assist Nigeria in fighting crises. Also, on March 6, 2012 the United States Commission on International Religious Freedom had a meeting at the Transcorp Hilton with some religious leaders on what American Government can do to help Nigeria achieve peaceful co-existence and promote human dignity.⁴⁴

In addition to the above, the Department of Mission and Dialogue of the Catholic Secretariat of Nigeria (CSN), has created a forum for dialogue between Catholic and Muslim women. The department has also initiated dialogue between Catholic and Muslim youths. And a lot of Non-Governmental Organisations are springing up and seeking recognition on a regular basis. Dialogue should and is used to help people resolve long lasting conflicts and to build deeper understanding of contentious issues. Dialogue is never about judging, weighing or making decisions but it is about understanding and learning.⁴⁵ Dialogue dispels stereotypes, builds trust, and enables people to be open to perspectives that are very different from their own. It is one sure way of healing memories and wounded hearts. In dialogue, parties are educated, informed, become aware and understand each other's beliefs or faiths the more.

The Church as reiterated is in dialogue with the Federation of Muslim Women Association in Nigeria (FOMWAN). Archbishop John Cardinal Onaiyekan referred to international efforts like the famous letter on "a common word" by over 250 high level Muslim leaders from all over the world, the Christian-Muslim dialogue initiatives from Saudi Arabia and Jordan, the visit of the Saudi King to Pope Benedict XVI in the Vatican. The directorate of Interfaith and Ecumenism of the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) is charged with the responsibilities of Ecumenical and interfaith dialogue.⁴⁶

To substantiate the above citation, it suffices to remind ourselves of the preamble of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria which states that "We the people of the Federal Republic of Nigeria having firmly and solemnly resolved: to live in unity and harmony as one indivisible and indissoluble sovereign Nation under God dedicated to promoting good government and welfare of all persons in our country on the principles of freedom, equality, justice and for the purpose of consolidating the unity of our people." The above quotation apparently suggests that before unity and harmony can be enhanced, dialogue among various religious faiths is necessary. After all, Nigeria is made up of a number of religious faiths such that section 14 of the 1999 Constitution states that "the Government of the Federation or of a state shall not adopt any religion as a state religion". This means that everyone is entitled to adopt whichever religion he/she desires without any coercion from anybody or group of people.

In dialogue, the religious leaders seek for a relationship in order to expose misunderstanding and to break barriers that separate and create hostility and conflict. The parties converse to resolve particular problems or foster cooperation in dealing with or preventing religious crises. Each partner learns from the rich store of wisdom of the other and each expresses his/her deepest conviction in the faith that has a truth worth sharing with each other. Dialogue aims at growth of common concern and also increases awareness that people need each other. It forms part of the realisation that the way in which people recognise and adore God should be intimately connected with the way in which they cherish each other. They are made to understand that the God of love whom they honour and uphold is the same God being sought when they honour and uphold their brother. Dialogue leads to exchange of information and insight with each other by deepening and strengthening the knowledge of each other and of religious truth. No religion claims absolute truth.

2. Peace Education: Peace Education is another key principle of comparative religion. It is the deliberate attempt to educate children and adults in the dynamics of conflict and the promotion of peacemaking skills in homes, schools, and communities, using all the channels and instruments of socialisation. It sets out to address this culture of violence and aggression and to inculcate values of non-violent change among young persons and adults alike. It opens up people's eyes and minds to see and understand actions taken and their consequences. Children and young persons have to know what peace is and guard themselves against embracing or being used to create violence. Through peace education, human beings could be taught to suppress their instinctive nature of being violent and instead strengthen their spirit-oriented nature so that it becomes dominant.

Peace education is an investment in the younger generations, and attests to the fact that by educating younger minds in the virtues of peace, the skills of conflict analysis and management, identification of conflicts and sources of conflicts,

are more peaceable future could be secured for humanity. Through the harmonising process of teaching and learning, peace education is out to enlighten students or the young and adults concerning the ills that confront Nigerians on daily basis. The inculcation or teaching of subjects such as religion and history, music, art and literature or similar subjects could help advance and promote the needed peace in a multi-cultural society as Northern Nigeria. These subjects could teach pupils or students to respect other's opinions and beliefs or faiths. They could also teach them to love, forgive, reconcile and value other's religions as well.

History should teach us to respond to the various historical events in the past which have tended to divide rather than unite us. History has too many lessons for us to learn. The stories of ugly of war, the agony, the pain, the displacement, the loss of lives and property should be enough reason we should shun religious violence. The knowledge been taught should make us have respect for others. Music can also be used to teach peace education. Music has messages that can change one's attitude or orientation, therefore music that promote unity only should be encouraged or sung and that which have divisions tenets or undertones should be discouraged and not sung at all.

Similarly, drawing, paintings, designs, cartoons (graffiti) et cetera can also help portray or convey messages of peace and, at another time conflict, so art works that depict the beauty of peace and harmony should be encouraged. Peace education inculcates in individual's positive attitudes for the attainment of peace. Such attitudes according to Gamut, affects our responses to conflict and the ways we look at and do things like to value human dignity. All religions value human life so young persons should have the sense of work for their own lives and that of others. They should be taught to do unto others what they would like it done unto them (the Golden Rule). They should also be taught to respect other beliefs (as reiterated), social background and family background. Younger persons or religious adherents should be taught to know and feel what others feel to image the feelings and viewpoints of others. They should also be taught certain skills: enquiry, communication, critical thinking skills which will equip them to be peace builders (though this is a gradual process).⁴⁷

Peace education can also be done through informal settings like during farm work, leisure, through socialisation and initiation processes within the community in family setting, community meetings et cetera. On the whole, it suffices to submit that a culture of peace is built from values, attitudes, behaviours and ways of life based on non-violence, respect for life, liberty, justice, solidarity, tolerance, human rights, equality between adherents before God, appreciation of religious diversity and respect and love for others.

3. The Effectiveness of Justice: The effectiveness of justice as a key principle of comparative religion is major tool for resolving religious crises in a society. Justice means right and fair behaviour or treatment. The quality of being reasonable, to deal with somebody properly and in an appropriate manner. For peace to reign supreme in Northern Nigeria, justice must be ensured. We already mentioned dialogue, that is conversation between the two parties, and now add that once the transgressing party is ready to make peace, the requirement of justice is ensured or assured. Do not seek revenge, do not impose restrictions and embargoes, by all means keep an eye on the repressor but at the same time try to and improve his situation.

Actions that discriminate against individuals or other faiths arbitrary or without a justifiable basis violates the principle of justice. The treatment of other religions or beliefs or faiths as not authentic, untrue is totally unacceptable. Everyone is created equal before the sight of the Almighty and there is no religion that is valued above another, therefore, fair or equal treatment of all citizens irrespective of religious affiliation is highly recommended. Impartial, fair and equal treatment of every human being is the virtue enshrined in both Christian and Muslim religions is the demand of justice. No wonder, the preamble to the 1999 Nigerian Constitution as reiterated, emphasises "...to live in unity and harmony as one indissoluble sovereign nation under God dedicated to promoting good government and welfare of all persons in our country on the principles of freedom, equality, justice and for the purpose of consolidating the unity of our people."⁴⁸

In addition to the above, the 1999 constitution does not favour any religion above another. It emphasizes freedom of worship-section 38(1) however reads "every person shall be entitled to freedom of thought, conscience and religion including freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom (either alone or in community with others, and in public or in private) to manifest and propagate his religion or belief in worship, teaching, practice and observance. Section 38 subsection 14 therefore, provides for freedom of thought, conscience and religion. This presupposes that there should not be state religion, no discrimination and the sort, whatsoever.

In another vein, for peace to thrive due process must be followed when conducting disciplinary action against an erring party under investigation, justice must be ensured. Justice here means the punishment awarded must be in such manner that any reasonable or dispassionate man would attest to fair and just or disinterested verdict. If the perpetrators of the heinous acts are brought to book, that is, punished or made to face the wrath of the law, then justice will have been

ensured, justice is therefore another potent tool or instrument of ensuring peace and stability in Northern Nigeria.

4. Religious Teachings/Doctrines: This is another major principle of comparative religion. Christians and Moslems alike have religious doctrines or teachings that can promote peace and stability in Northern Nigeria. For instance, Christianity teaches respect to authority and to give to Caesar what belongs to Caesar and to God what belongs to God. The basis for executive authority is laid in Romans 13:1 and 2 where Paul said “let every soul be subject unto the higher powers. For there is no power but of God: the powers that be are ordered by God. Whosoever therefore, resisted the power, resisted the ordinance of God: and they that resist shall receive to themselves damnation”.⁴⁹

Similarly, in 1 Peter 2:13-14, Peter directed Christians to “be subject to every kind of human order, whether it be to the king as the foremost, or government as sent by him, as a vengeance on the wicked and a reward to the just” (see also Matthew 22:19 - 21; 17:25-27; 1 Peter 2:18, 1 Cor. 7:21-24, Ephesians 6: 5-9, 1 Timothy 6:1-2; 1 Peter 2: 13-17; Deuteronomy 17:12-13; Romans 13:1-2). Liberal learning towards authority in the Christendom will therefore cause a Christian to gain respect for the privacy of others, realising that certain aspects of other people’s lives do not fall under his jurisdiction.⁵⁰ Hence, he would not attempt to take over the power of the state to sanction deviant behaviour, nor would he try to abate certain conduct, which through it offends Christian doctrine, is absolutely within the regulatory purview of temporal authority. By virtue of this doctrine of compliance to temporal authority, Christianity endorses compliance with the economic, political and social order sanctioned by temporal authority, provided that does not interfere with its worship.

Islam, on the other hand is not just a religion, but a way of life that encompasses the entire gamut of the economic, judicial, political and cultural lives of its Umma (faithful); hence its definition as “total submission to the will of Allah (God) as revealed by the prophetic message of Muhammad. The totality of Islamic regulation of the lives of Moslems is comprehensively captured by Olayimola who notes that “Islam does not admit a narrow view of religion by restricting it within the limits of worship, specific rituals and spiritual beliefs. In its precise meaning, Islam is not only a religion; it is a way of life that regulates all the aspects of life on the scale of the individual and the nation. Islam is a social order, philosophy of life, a system of economic rules and government”.⁵¹

Islam clearly establishes man’s duties and rights in all relationships—a clear system of worship, civil rights, laws of marriage and divorce, inheritance, code of behaviour, law of economy, laws of governance, laws of war and peace, of buying and selling and laws of relations and co-existence with one another, parents, children, relatives, neighbours, guests, Muslims, non-Muslims and brethren. An apt distinction on the perception of these two religions to temporal and religious authority is captured by Abikan, who posited that “A Christian for instance may be prepared in the notion of giving to Caesar and God what respectively belong to them, to limit his right to religious freedom to matters of faith and worship only.”⁵²

A person from the West may also be contented with the Western compartmentalisation of life into religious and temporal. A Muslim on the other hand would view religion as covering all the facets of life. This is because his spiritual and moral worth is tested against his daily interaction with others at the congregational prayers, in marital union, in the pursuit of his legitimate livelihood and in the holding of public responsibilities, amongst others.”⁵³ With this rigid representation of Islam as a comprehensive tool for the regulation of the entire lifestyle of its faithful, there is no room for separation between spiritual and temporal affairs for those who choose to be pious Muslims. This absolutist characterisation of Islam is the reason some adherents like the “Wahhabi” go extreme. Any religious doctrines or teachings are potent tools for resolving religious crises in Northern Nigeria.

5. Education on Religious Tolerance: This is also one of the major principles of comparative religion. Religious Tolerance is considered by many as the panacea for peace, harmony, stability and development in Northern Nigeria. Religious intolerance is the major problem we experience in Nigeria and this is because people lack adequate and proper knowledge and understanding of other people’s religions. All religions are true and man cannot live without religion so an attitude of respect and tolerance must be ensured. Intolerance is rooted in ignorance and fear of the unknown or other religions. It is closely linked to an exaggerated sense of self-worth and pride. In order to dispel this hostile or uncompromising attitude, education builds tolerance through education in all ages: at home, in schools, in the workplace, in law-enforcement and legal training and not least in entertainment and on the information highways.⁵³

One must not develop fallacious argument, lie with statistics and manipulate public opinion with misinformation and prejudice. Bigotry, stereotyping, stigmatising, insults and racial jokes are examples of individual expressions of intolerance to which people/adherents of a particular religion are subjected to daily. This leads the victims in pursuit of revenge. To do away with these, individuals should become aware of the link between their behaviour and the victim’s cycle of mistrust and violence in society. Each of us should begin by asking: am I a tolerant person? Do I stereotype people? Do I reject those who are different from me? Do I blame my problems on them?

Nigerians need to have a change of mind and attitude towards fellow citizens who are not of their religious stock. No adherents or believers of a particular religion should feel more important than the other in the community. People must eschew xenophobic attitudes - derogatory name calling, discrimination, stereotyping should be discouraged. This will go nip the crises in the bud and in turn promote the much-needed peace, stability and harmony in a developing country as Nigeria.

Recommendations

Owing from the findings above, the study hereby recommends that since religious tolerance and harmony is both legally sanctioned and socially inevitable (as the world cannot be composed of one religion or culture), every religious group has the right to uninhibited religious practice). This must be done with commensurate or reciprocal respect for the rights of other faithful to practice their own religious traditions; provided that such does not constitute any derogation to the right of others to observe their own rituals). Therefore, the establishment and sustenance of a neo-religious educational praxis in our children and youth, as well as a commensurate programme of re-orientation of the adult population. There is also, the need to reform the current curriculum on religious studies, which hitherto privileged the exclusive teaching of dogmatic Christian and Islamic doctrines, to a new praxis that would build in comparative religious studies and expose students and pupils to basic principles of Christianity, Islam and traditional religions in order to instill in them religious harmony and moral instructions.

Furthermore, religious communities must understand that there is no alternative to inter-faith dialogue, as there can never be a universal religion or an exclusive society for adherents of a particular religion. Therefore, all religious communities must educate their clergy on the need for religious harmony and the toleration of other faiths, while also educating that clergy and laity on the need to keep their sermons within the realm of moderation and modesty. There is need to strengthen interfaith dialogue at the national, state and local levels in order to prevent future manifestations of religious violence. The Nigerian Inter-Religious Council (NIRC), together with relevant faith-based organizations and civil society organisations should constantly engage in dialogue with the various religious communities, while also serving as a plat form for conflict analysis and early warning on religious violence. There is need for government to develop a long-term strategy for the management of religious conflict/violence. This should be done by convening an ad hoc ‘National Summit Religion’ with the primary mandate of developing a National Policy/Strategy on Religion and the State (NPSRS). This summit should be drawn from major stakeholders from the three major religious practitioners as well as state representatives.

The summit could work on preliminary issues and subsequently recommend the establishment of standing “National Commission on Religion” (NCR) to continue a dialogue that would crystallise into the development of an NPSRS. This NPSRS would discuss issues of secularity, thereby delineating the role of religion in state affairs and vice-versa. It should also design the rules of state-religion engagement in order to establish clear, consistent and predictable standards in state-religion relations as a basis for fairness and equity in the relationship between religion and the state. It would settle issues of proselytisation (encompassing all modes and methods of preaching), mutual engagement by all religious groups, the methods, means and extent of worship involving consensus on acceptable and unacceptable modes of worship), punishment for acts that trigger religious violence and a comprehensive ‘Religious Conflicts Early Warning System (RCEWS)’ that would configure an intelligence gathering and evaluation system on religious violence, and also design the means to its timely containment through preventive dialogue.

The NPSRS should also establish a de-radicalisation programme that will gradually eliminate the ideology of terror and also conduct psychological profiling of remnants of radicalised religious cadres. This policy should also design a strategy for the disarmament, de-radicalisation and rehabilitation of religious militants who have not just been brainwashed, but have taken religious combat as a vocation. Once these issues are consensually agreed on by all religious stakeholders, the delegitimisation of the drivers of religious violence by constitutional, legislative and policy reforms would become an easy endeavour. This is because there would be an informed consensus on the religious acts or omissions that constitute criminal offences and should therefore be prohibited by all religious groups.

Security personnel should also intensify their efforts at the borders where small arms are being smuggled into the country. If the perpetrators of this violence lack arms to fight, of course violence would be reduced to its barest minimum. In other words, if one is bereft of weapons, he cannot kill with bare hands, therefore, small arms should be prevented from getting into the hands of these die-hard adherents. For example, Boko Haram is speculated to have in their possession equal lethal weapons than even the Nigerian military. Security at the borders should be cemented. These and other similar recommendations should be enforced in order to realise the much needed stability, harmony and peace for a better, healthier

and blissful posterity. God help us.

Conclusion

Nigeria is a multi-ethnic country with religious diversities. A state with population of about 450 million people subscribes to Christianity, Islam or traditional religion or beliefs. Religion is what defines man's being in the universe; this is why Nigerians are so passionate when it comes to matters of religion. In fact, the essence of religion cannot be overemphasized. Apart from emphasising its intrinsic value of guaranteeing a blissful life hereafter, it plays the positive role of ensuring peace, love, justice, handwork, honesty, hope, tolerance, forgiveness et cetera as the study of comparative religious expose. Paradoxically, these powerful and positive ingredients or elements are lacking by adherents of these religions in Nigeria, our behaviour and attitudes betray our religiosity. This has to a greater extent thwarted the much-desired peace, harmony and stability in the Nigeria society.

The study however focused on the role of comparing these religions to a view of harnessing its positive values or tenets or doctrines to further peace, stability and harmony. It is suggested that dialogue, peace education, justice and religious teachings or doctrines and tolerance are key panacea to attaining sustainable peace for development to thrive in Nigeria. We need to understand that religion permeates beliefs and practice or behaviour-thinking and action. If the above tools are employed in Nigeria, the masses will live to enjoy the essence of their existence-to live a happier, joyful and blissful life here and hereafter.

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